

MARRIAGE LIFE THROUGH “BHRIGU NANDI NADI”

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Abstract:

In this article, it is to learn about the “Marriage Confirmation by Bhriugu Nandi Nadi” method. Whether a person will get married or not can be answered very simply in this method. In this method, only four planets are taken into account to check the marriage confirmation of a person.

Jupiter: Jupiter is the life governing planet for Male so Jupiter is taken as Lagna for Male.

Venus: Venus is the life governing planet for Female. So, Venus is taken as Lagna for Female and In male horoscope Venus should be taken as wife

Saturn: Saturn is a Karmic (Karaka of karmic) planet for both Male & Female. So Saturn can be taken to determine whether marriage will take place according to karma in the horoscopes of both men and women.

Mars: In female horoscope Mars should be taken as Husband

Note: The relationship between these above four planets can determine whether one will get married or not.

Key Words: Sun, Moon, Mars, Mercury, Jupiter, Venus, Saturn, Rahu (Dragon’s Head) & Kethu (Dragon’s Tail)

Introduction:

In Bhriugu Nandi Nadi method when considering the results, the following points are observed in Natal chart (Rasi Chart) for confirmation of marriage of Men & Women.

In Men’s horoscope

- If Venus is placed in places of 1,5,9,3,7,11,2,12 to Jupiter or Saturn

In Women’s horoscope

- If Mars is placed in places of 1,5,9,3,7,11,2,12 to Venus or Saturn
 1,5,9 - Same direction (Being in the same direction)
 3,7,11 - Opposite direction- Aspect each other
 2,12 - Adjacent Houses

Chart No 1

Sa(R) Ra	Mo		
	MAN 08-10-1968(5.30E) 1..30am.Palani TN 77E32E 10N28		Mars Jup
	As	Ve Me(R)	Ke Sun

In Men’s horoscope

Rule: If Venus is placed in places of 1,5,9,3,7,11,2,12 to Jupiter or Saturn

Analysis from the Chart:

According to the rule, marriage took place due to Jupiter placed in 11th to Venus. Here Jupiter and Venus aspects each other on the basis of 3, 11

Since, the Rule is applied accurately.

Chart No 2

		Ma	
Ve	MAN 11-02-1991(5.30E) 09.02pm.Palani TN 77E32E 10N28		Ke Ju
Su Me Sa Ra			
Mo			As

In Men’s horoscope

Rule: If Venus is placed in places of 1,5,9,3,7,11,2,12 to Jupiter or Saturn

Analysis from the Chart:

According to the rule, marriage took place due to Saturn placed in 12th to Venus. Here Saturn and Venus adjacent to each other on the basis of 2, 12

Since, the Rule is applied accurately. Marriage will get delayed as Saturn is involved in the combination and marriage happened as per Karma (Karmic planet – Saturn)

Chart No 3

Ve	Me Su	Ke	
Sa	WOMAN 03-05-1993(5.30E) 10.33pm.Salem TN 78E10E 11N39		Ma
As	Ra		JuR Mo

In Women’s horoscope

Rule: If Mars is placed in places of 1,5,9,3,7,11,2,12 to Venus or Saturn

Analysis from the Chart:

According to the rule, marriage took place due to Mars placed in 5th to Venus. Here Mars and Venus are in the same direction on the basis of 1,5,9

Since, the Rule is applied accurately.

Chart No 4

Ra	JuR		
	MAN 31-08-1987(5.30E) 08.45am.Salem TN 78E10E 11N39		Ma Su Ve Me
	Sa Mo		As Ke

In Men’s horoscope

Rule: If Venus is placed in places of 1,5,9,3,7,11,2,12 to Jupiter or Saturn

Analysis from the Chart:

According to the rule, marriage took place due to Jupiter placed in 9th to Venus. Here Jupiter and Venus are in the same direction on the basis of 1,5,9

Since, the Rule is applied accurately.

Chart No 5

Ju	Ke	MaR	
	MAN 28-12-1975(5.30E) 09.16pm.Palani TN 77E32E 10N28		SaR As
Me Su	Ve	Ra Mo	

In Men’s horoscope

Rule: If Venus is placed in places of 1,5,9,3,7,11,2,12 to Jupiter or Saturn

Analysis from the Chart:

According to the rule, marriage took place due to Jupiter placed in 5th to Venus. Here Jupiter and Venus are in the same direction on the basis of 1,5,9

Since, the Rule is applied accurately.

Chart No 6

			JuR
Mo	WOMAN 01-01-1990(5.30E) 09.15am.Palani TN 77E32E 10N28		Ke
As Ra VeR MeR			
Sa Su	Ma		

In Women's horoscope

Rule: If Mars is placed in places of 1,5,9,3,7,11,2,12 to Venus or Saturn

Analysis from the Chart:

According to the rule, marriage took place due to Mars placed in 11th to Venus. Here Mars and Venus are in the opposite direction related on the basis of 3,7,11

Since, the Rule is applied accurately.

Chart No 7

Me Ke Su Ma Sa		Ve	As
	WOMAN 04-04-1996(5.30E) 11.30am.Palani TN 77E32E 10N28		
Ju			Ra Mo

In Women's horoscope

Rule: If Mars is placed in places of 1,5,9,3,7,11,2,12 to Venus or Saturn

Analysis from the Chart:

According to the rule, marriage took place due to Mars placed in 11th to Venus. Here Mars and Venus are in the opposite direction related on the basis of 3,7,11

Since, the Rule is applied accurately.

Chart No 8

Ke		Ma	
As	MAN 09-10-1958(5.30E) 03.01pm.Nilakottai TN 77E52E 10N10		
			Mo
	Sa	Ju	Ve Su Me Ra

In Men's horoscope

Rule: If Venus is placed in places of 1,5,9,3,7,11,2,12 to Jupiter or Saturn

Analysis from the Chart:

According to the rule, marriage took place due to Jupiter placed 2nd to Venus. Here Jupiter and Venus are in the adjacent houses on the basis of 2,12

Since, the Rule is applied accurately.

Chart No 9

	Ma		Ve
	MAN 04-08-1990(5.30E) 05.44am.Palani TN 77E32E 10N28		Ju As Ke Su
Ra			Me
SaR Mo			

In Men's horoscope

Rule: If Venus is placed in places of 1,5,9,3,7,11,2,12 to Jupiter or Saturn

Analysis from the Chart:

According to the rule,

- marriage took place due to Jupiter placed in 12th to Venus.
- marriage took place due to Saturn placed in 7th to Venus

Here Jupiter and Venus are in the adjacent houses on the basis of 2,12 and also Saturn aspects from 7th on the basis of 3,7,11

Since, the Rule is applied accurately.

Chart No 10

SaR			
Ke	WOMAN		As
Ju	25-10-1997(5.30E) 11.35pm.virudhunagar TN 77E57 09N36		Mo Ra
	Ma Ve	Me Su	

In Women's horoscope

Rule: If Mars is placed in places of 1,5,9,3,7,11,2,12 to Venus or Saturn

Analysis from the Chart:

According to the rule, marriage took place due to Mars placed in same house of Venus. (1st house). Here Mars and Venus are in the same direction related on the basis of 1, 5, 9 Since, the Rule is applied accurately.

Conclusion:

There are various methods used in Astrology to determine One's marriage confirmation. But, Brighu Nandhi Nadi method is using simplest rules to determine the marriage confirmation. Generally, the people are getting oscillated as to whether marriage will confirm or not. Predictions will be made easily for them using the above rules. Further, it is very useful to all Astrologers & all clients for easy prediction.

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